

SEMANTIC AND FUNCTIONAL ASPECTS OF LEXICAL DOUBLETS IN ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

Language is a natural phenomenon that grows in every era. As time goes by grammatical, phonetic, lexical, semantic, etc. in one language for various reasons changes can be observed. The fact that the language undergoes such changes is the growth of the language indicates that it is going. The following is also a dictionary of the English language a brief research was conducted on the reasons and factors for the change in its composition.

All language is social in nature and therefore it is outside society cannot exist and cannot develop. Language, first of all, its vocabulary is a means of communication between people that actively influences the formation. At the same time, language is a sign system with its own internal laws we must not forget that in any advanced language, the same idea applies to the situation can be expressed differently.

A linguistic doublet is also a doublet in language or simply a doublet or -in linguistics, doublets are the same or close in meaning, etymologically same lexical units and groups of units are understood. Besides The creative basis is semantic and functional in the process of evolutionary development of language stylistically different. On the contrary, doublets are phonetic and morphological or syntactically different, but have the same meaning it is also formed using words or combinations.

Examples of doublets, for example, from the Russian language:

«Замóк» and «зámок»

«Холоп» and «хлопец»

«Узел» and «вензель»

«Надёжный» and «надежда»

«Обволакивать» and «облако»

«Горожанин» and «гражданин»

Also, doublets, both words of which consist of hybrid words there is:

«Стандарт» and «штандарт» (First word - english, second - german)

«Регистр» and «реестр» (First word - latin, second - polish)

In this case, both words can be borrowed from the same language, for example - the word doublet itself and a paired word (both Gallicisms) or, for example, mixer and mixer (both anglicisms).

Doublets appear most often in Romance languages, here etymologically related folk Latin, classical Latin and words of mixed origin often they live together in the nest of making one word. The first, as a rule, is the vernacular strongly modified by linguistic laws (elision, prosthesis, assimilation, modified stress, etc.), and classical book Latinism is almost different from its ancient counterpart doesn't make a difference. "When two or more words have the same etymological root, i.e. originate from the same root word, but have different phonological forms or colloquial versions, they are called doublets or etymological twins (or triplets). Although these pairs of words are not the same, they have similar meanings. They enter the language in different ways."¹

There are two distinct types of folk etymology in doublet words. In the first case, the assimilated (rarely native) word is close to it in terms of sound according to the word model of the native language, which is different in terms of origin will be broken and revised. Lexical counterparts are one of the oldest and most complete lexico-semantic categories.

Lexical doublets in general linguistics, Germanic studies, Russian linguistics and were widely studied by many Turkic scholars, for example, in the middle of the 19th century, in-depth studies on English linguistics were carried out by W. V. Skit (1882), O. F. Emerson (1915); R. Barber (R. Barbier, 1922); A. Baugh (1957); D. Bilber (1988); AJ Bliss (1966); J. L. Brook (GL Brook, 1958); A. Kunin (A. Coonin, 1940) and many other scientists we can cite.

The issue of lexical doublets in the Uzbek language Sh. Rakhmatullayev (2006), A. Hojiyev (1981), R. Kongurov (1980), E. Begmatov (1985), M. Mirtojiyev (2010),

In the works of I. Kochkortoyev (1977), B. Daniyarov (2020) and others, one or another level details are covered. O. Yusupov (2020) is in English and Uzbek conducted a functional-semantic and linguocultural study of doublets. Azim Hajiyev "Annotated Dictionary of Linguistic Terms" doublets in French "Doublet - double" is derived from the word "double" and has the same equal semantic content states that they are linguistic units.

When it comes to lexical doublets in English, such units are later can pass to a literary standard, for example English tip-top (excellent, first class) or hocus-pocus (hocus-pocus, fraud). Such words have been in the language for centuries can be saved. Based on the above, we only of any language learning the standard vocabulary gives us the language itself and the spirit of the people who speak it we can conclude that we will not have a complete idea about it.

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¹ Хомяков В.А. Нестандартная лексика в структуре английского языка национального периода: автореф. дис. ... д-ра филол. наук. Л., 1980. 39 с. 10.